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Employed in Temporary Jobs for at Least 5 Years in the Period 2018-2022

They decreased on average by -4.73% between 2018 and 2022 in the Italian regions

Istat calculates the value of those employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years. The variable is defined as the percentage of fixed-term employees and collaborators who have started their current job at least 5 years ago out of the total fixed-term employees and collaborators. The data refers to the period between 2018 and 2022 in the Italian regions.

Ranking of the regions by value of those employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years in 2022. Calabria is in first place by value of those employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years in 2022 with a value of 27.60, followed by Basilicata with 27.50 units, and from Sicily with 27.40 units. In the middle of the table are Valle d'Aosta with a value of 17.20 units, followed by Friuli Venezia Giulia with 15.90 and Emilia Romagna with 15.40 units. Piedmont closes the ranking with a value of 11.20 units, followed by Lombardy with a value of 10.80 units and Veneto with a value of 9.50 units.

Ranking of the regions by value of the percentage change in those employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years between 2018 and 2022. Basilicata is in first place by value of the percentage change in those employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years between 2018 and 2022 with a variation equal to +28.50% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 21.40 units up to a value of 27.50 units. Umbria follows with a variation from an amount equal to 13.70 units up to a value of 15.20 units between 2018 and 2022 corresponding to a variation from an amount of 1.50 units equal to 10.95%. In third place is Sardinia with a variation from 10.60 units in 2018 up to a value of 11.70 units or equal to 1.10 units corresponding to a variation of 10.38%. In the middle of the table are Campania with a variation from 22.00 units in 2018 up to 22.10 units in 2022 or equal to 0.10 units corresponding to +0.45%. Friuli Venezia Giulia follows with a variation from an amount of 16.40 units in 2014 up to 15.90 units in 2022 or corresponding to a variation of -0.50 units equal to an amount of -3.05%. Also in the middle of the table are the Marche with a variation from an amount of 14.10 units in 2018 up to 13.50 units in 2022 or corresponding to a variation of -0.60 units equal to a variation of -4.26%. Veneto closes the ranking with a variation from an amount of 12.30 units up to a value of 9.50 units or equal to a variation of -2.80 units corresponding to a value of -22.76%. Liguria follows with a variation from an amount from 16.50 units in 2018 up to a value of 12.70 units in 2022 or corresponding to an amount of -2.80 units equal to a value of -22.76%. Liguria follows with a variation from an amount of 16.50 units up to a value of 12.70 units or equal to a variation of -3.80 units corresponding to a value of -23.03%. Molise closes the ranking with a variation from an amount of 15.90 units up to a value of 11.80 units equal to a variation of -4.10 units corresponding to a variation of -25.79%. On average the value decreased for the Italian regions from 18.08 in 2018 up to a value of 17.22 units in 2022 or equal to a variation of -0.86 units corresponding to -4.73%.

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Employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years in the Italian macro-regions. The value of those employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years in the Islands decreased from an amount of 28.40 in 2018 to an amount of 23.10 units in 2022 or equal to a corresponding variation of -5.30 units at a variation of -18.66%. The value of employed people in the South decreased from 25.00 in 2018 to 22.90 units in 2022 or equal to a variation of -2.10 units corresponding to -8.40%. The value of those employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years decreased from an amount of 23.30 units in 2018 to a value of 22.70 units in 2022 or equal to a value of -0.60 units corresponding to a value by -2.58%. The value of those employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years in the Italian macro-regions in the Center decreased from an amount of 18.40 units in 2018 to a value of 17.00 units in 2022 or equal to a variation of -1.40 units corresponding to a variation of -7.61%. The value of those employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years in the Italian macro-regions in the North-East decreased from an amount of 14.40 units to a value of 13.50 units or equal to a reduction of -0.90 unit corresponding to a variation of -6.25%. The value of those employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years in the Italian macro-regions in the North decreased from an amount of 12.70 units in 2018 to a value of 12.30 units in 2022 or equal to a variation of -0.40 units corresponding to a variation of -3.15%. The value of those employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years in the Italian macro-regions in the North-West decreased from an amount of 11.00 units to a value of 11.20 units or corresponding to a variation of 0.20 units equal to 1.82%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Marche, Umbria, Piedmont, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Veneto, Liguria, Lombardy, Sardinia, Emilia Romagna, Tuscany, Trentino Alto Adige, Abruzzo, Valle d'Aosta;
- Cluster 2: Puglia, Calabria, Sicily, Basilicata, Molise, Campania, Lazio.

The regions of Cluster 2 appear to be dominant in terms of the average value of the variable analyzed compared to the regions of Cluster 1. The following ordering of the clusters therefore occurs: C2>C1. We can therefore note that the value of employed people who remain in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years tends to be higher in the regions of Southern Italy compared to the regions of Central-Northern Italy. However there are exceptions. In particular, Lazio, which despite being a central region, is part of Cluster 2; Sardinia and Abruzzo which are part of Cluster 1. Therefore there is a clear representation of the gap between Central-Northern Italy and Southern Italy.

Conclusions. Obviously we must consider that the value of those employed in fixed-term jobs for at least 5 years appears to be higher in absolute value in the regions of Central-North compared to the regions of Southern Italy. In fact, even if the percentage values tend to be high in Southern Italy, since the indicator is calculated on the total number of employed people, and since employed people tend to be higher in the Central-Northern regions compared to the Southern Italian regions, it follows that the absolute value is higher in the northern regions than in the southern ones. However, this indicator confirms, if any were needed, the presence of a crack between the northern labor market and the southern labor market, with a prejudice that weighs on the southern regions. A confirmation of the inequality of working conditions manifests not only in the contractual dimension as well as in salary recognition.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

